

Analysis of renewable energy infrastructure representations in OpenStreetMap

Luisa Lo Presti^{1,*} and Peter Mooney²

¹ Hamilton Institution, Maynooth University, Ireland; luisa.lopresti.2024@mumail.ie

² Department of Computer Science, Maynooth University, Ireland; peter.mooney@mu.ie

* Author to whom correspondence should be addressed.

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Building a more environmentally sustainable future requires continued development of renewable energy infrastructure. Support for the renewable energy transition calls for the availability of reliable data about energy supply, infrastructures, and environmental impact [1]. OpenStreetMap (OSM) can meet these data requirements. In this work, we describe our research on evaluating the OSM database as a source of data for the study of wind and solar energy infrastructures. As a case-study, we consider two European countries, namely Belgium and Ireland but the work is extendible to other countries and regions. Data within OSM is well-known to have a diverse level of completeness and granularity [2]. However, considering OSM's vibrant mapping communities coupled with both (a) the environmental visibility of wind and solar energy infrastructures, and (b) their relatively limited number compared to other built infrastructures, it is reasonable to assume that the majority of these installations are well mapped within OSM. OSM energy-related objects are widely reported under the "power" tag, with available key-value combinations to identify wind and solar sources. Wind turbines are commonly tagged as "power=generator" and "generator:source=wind", while solar farms are identified as "power=plant" and "plant:source=solar". Over the past few years, the OSM community has expanded its mapping efforts for these tags. For instance, the OSM Tag Info page for solar plants shows an increase from under 5,000 instances in 2020 to over 60,000 by mid-2024 globally. Furthermore, the geographical distribution of these tags highlights a significant concentration of mapping activities in Europe compared to other regions. By combining OSM data with the CORINE Land Cover (CLC) inventory, we consider two research questions. Firstly, we seek to identify common mapping errors and tagging issues associated with wind and solar energy infrastructures representation within OSM. This involves examining geometries and tagging mistakes while evaluating the accuracy and completeness of infrastructures data. Secondly, we perform a geographical analysis to consider the distribution of infrastructures across various CLC, seeking to detect patterns around land covers and renewable energy infrastructures.

Our methodology is summarized as follows: OSM data, in PBF format, is downloaded from GeoFabrik. For our initial investigations, we consider Ireland and Belgium due to local knowledge and their manageable data sizes. Analyses are performed using Python and the *osmium* library, and source code is openly available on GitHub in documented Jupyter notebooks [3]. We answer our research questions using three key steps:

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1. Assess available wind and solar infrastructures in OSM for the correctness of OSM data types and potential geometric errors.
2. Differentiate between individual installations and larger “farms”, to evaluate the quality and completeness of OSM data.
3. Investigate commonalities around land use surrounding renewable energy infrastructures using CLC.

At the outset, power-related data is extracted using the custom `PowerSourceHandler` class, developed by inheriting from `osmium SimpleHandler`. This class was designed to examine a PBF file and extract all OSM objects with “power” tag equal to “plant” or “generator”, yielding a full listing of all available power sources. We filter solar and wind sources based on the “generator:source” or “plant:source” tags. The accuracy of the OSM data types and geometries is checked before moving to “farms”.

To accurately differentiate single installations from farms, we analyze solar and wind sources separately due to their different geometric nature. We employ a point-in-polygon search with spatial indexes to assign nodes – of either wind or solar type – to intersecting areas of the same energy type. This process raises some geometric questions concerning the meaning of areas without nodes and with nodes not linked to any area. We observed several mapping and tagging issues: (a) not mapping individual panels within solar farms or defining turbines as circular areas, (b) nodes not associated with any area, (c) unlinked solar nodes representing private installations (rooftop solar panels or solar thermal collectors), (d) the absence of OSM areas or relations for turbines, frequently indicating incomplete mapping. This final issue is significant: currently, 91.4% of wind nodes in Belgium and around 87.4% in Ireland are not located within any mapped area. Considering the limited number of turbines included in OSM areas or relations, we employed spatial clustering on all turbines to identify wind farms and validate our findings by automatically comparing clusters with existing OSM areas and relations. As a density-based spatial clustering, DBSCAN (Density-based spatial clustering of applications with noise) is particularly well suited for this purpose. The algorithm requires us to specify the minimum number of samples in a cluster, and the maximum distance between two samples for them to belong to the same neighborhood. The latter is to be considered one of the most important parameters influencing results: considering the characteristics of onshore wind energy infrastructures, we define the maximum average distance for onshore turbines belonging to the same farm as 5 times the rotor diameter [4]. Despite the availability of the OSM tag “rotor:diameter” for reporting the exact value of the rotor diameter, this attribute is often not reported. Thus, we assume a diameter value of 130 meters for all turbines [4]. Comparing clustering results with OSM data allows us to evaluate quality and completeness of areas and relations, to identify new farms, and to extend existing linkages to unassigned infrastructures.

Due to their geometric nature, the same process cannot be applied to solar infrastructures. All remaining solar data are defined as areas, complicating the automated differentiation between individual installations and solar farms. Our methodology consists of two different processes, based on the value of the `power` tag (“generator” or “plant”). Although the OSM wiki guidelines state that solar farms should be tagged as “plant”, deviations from this standard are possible. To address this issue and avoid discarding valid data, we conduct an area-in-area search on solar generators. This approach assumes that if

a solar generator area encompasses multiple solar generators, it may denote a farm. This process enables us to identify a few tagging mistakes where the “generator” value was used instead of “plant”. Manual examination confirms the correctness of our approach. While it may be possible to apply the same approach on solar “plant”, this would cause a significant data loss, thus we opt for keeping all plant-objects. Ultimately, this decision is strongly dependent on the data accuracy requirements.

The refined datasets provide a comprehensive overview of wind and solar energy sources, facilitating further analyses into renewable energy. Relevant environmental considerations lay on the analysis of land uses around these infrastructures. We retrieved this information from the CORINE database, considering an intermediate level of land type detail (CORINE LABEL2). By evaluating land uses within an arbitrary 1000-meter buffer, we may identify consistent patterns as well as countries' peculiarities. In Belgium, around 18% of wind farms are located within 1000 meters from heterogeneous agricultural areas, while 17% and 15% are near urban fabric and arable land respectively. In Ireland, most wind farms are near pastures (~24%), scrub (~18%) and forests (~18%). We noticed how agricultural areas, in the form of heterogeneous agricultural areas, pastures, or arable land seem to prevail in both contexts. Notably, about 15% of Irish wind farms are close to inland wetlands, mainly peat bogs (CORINE LABEL3), which serve as a natural carbon storage. Figure 1 provides an example. In contrast, this proximity is minimal in Belgium (~0.3%). Monitoring infrastructure near these sensitive areas in Ireland is crucial to prevent negative impacts. For wind energy, artificial surfaces appear relevant only in Belgium; however, both countries have solar farms near urban fabric land cover. Within the buffer from solar infrastructures this LC appears ~19% of the time in Belgium and ~12% in Ireland. In Belgium, heterogeneous agricultural areas (~19%) and forests (~12%) are also significant, while pastures predominate in Ireland (~31%), followed by arable land (~16%). However, it is worth noticing that 56% of the Irish territory is classified as pasture LC. If planned well, the installation of solar infrastructures on various types of agricultural land may create agrivoltaic opportunities, with several potential benefits such as improved crop yields and reduced water usage and enhanced soil moisture retention.

This work considered how to assess and improve completeness and accuracy of renewable energy infrastructure data in OSM. Our analysis distinguishes between individual installations and larger farms, enhancing available data with spatial methodologies. Our based on density-based clustering for identifying wind farms allows evaluation of the OSM data. We employ geocomputation methods to associate solar panels to farms, mitigating tagging errors. We highlighted challenges stemming from inconsistent mapping practices, deviating from OSM guidelines for tag usage and geometry types. Despite these issues, the refined datasets offer comprehensive insights into wind and solar energy sources, enabling deeper analyses and assessment of their integration into the surrounding landscape.

Overall, our small study highlights strengths and limitations of OSM data for renewable energy analysis while offering practical tools (shared in Jupyter notebooks) to assess and enhance overall data quality. We find that OSM has great value and potential as a data source for those considering analysis of renewable energy infrastructure deployment, particularly in contexts where official data are lacking or not publicly available. Future work will include validating our approach for a larger set of countries and regions, while integrating further internal and external completeness and quality evaluations. The latter may be facilitated in countries where renewable energy data are openly available, such as

Norway. We did not process the OSM for larger countries but checked the OHSOME dashboard [5] for more insights. According to this dashboard, since July 2021 wind generator mapping in Ireland and Belgium has risen by 36.5% and 14.3% respectively, while solar generator objects have grown by 1154% and 448%. Significant growing trends are present also in other European countries for the same period. Finally, further research is needed to assess the completeness of other infrastructure-related tags, such as operator, installation date, and generator output values.

Figure 1. Example of wind farms near peat bogs in Ireland. Red lines mark 1000-meter buffers around wind farms, with land cover shown according to CLC. The map in the bottom right corner highlights the zoomed area with a blue circle.

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